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SUPPORTING SECONDARY STEM EDUCATION AND ATTRACTING STUDENTS TO SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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Is your science or engineering field known to secondary school teachers and students? We will show you some of our efforts to support secondary STEM teachers and students in their regular curriculum and to enrich their experience using up-to-date science and technology experiments. In a 5-minute overview we will present the main features our model for school – university cooperation in which school teachers with strong science and engineering backgrounds develop program content for high school students and for professional development of teacher colleagues in close cooperation with university experts. Content is focused on new topics in the school STEM curricula and linked to university R&D. Lesson materials are developed together with response groups of teachers and extensively tested in their classrooms and revised. This joint curriculum development turns out to be the best professional development for teaching the new curriculum topics. What are the benefits for the different stakeholders? How do we optimize them? What are our strengths and what are our difficulties?

Our outreach goals are: a) to support curriculum and professional development on new curriculum topics which can be linked to prominent university research areas, and b) to maintain strong connections between teachers and schools and the university.

After the introduction we will introduce three topics in short 7-minute video presentations which are each followed by 3 minutes of questions by the online workshop participants.

1) Lab-on-a-chip is one of the research topics studied intensively at University of Twente. Starting 10 years ago, STEM lesson series were developed by teachers and university researchers, tested in schools and revised and now routinely used in schools. The sophisticated practical kit provides equipment of professional quality with delicate glass devices. Students are enabled to become experienced with the microfluidic equipment, and to study fluid physics, electrochemistry and biological experiments. The number of high schools working with the kits is limited due to costs.

A new approach was found in easy-to-use techniques to facilitate students to design and produce their own Lab-on-a-chip devices. The basic version may be produced in matter of minutes, also by young children. Upper level high school students use the

more advanced designs, illustrating all principles of microfluidics. However, they can also design and produce their own Lab-on-a chip devices. Deposition of gold nanoparticles, using a quick reaction at room temperature, serves to characterize the flow patterns in the chips. This helps students to evaluate their design, and facilitates learning microfluidic concepts. In the online presentation, we demonstrate the approach and show images of classrooms where students apply these techniques and produce and test LoC devices with dyes or the gold nanoparticle reaction. In the break-out group after the presentations hands-on practicals are demonstrated and discussed in more detail, focusing on learning outcomes and possibilities for wider implementation in the countries and educational systems of workshop participants.

2) Quantum Suitcase Experiments were developed to support the teaching of quantum physics in secondary schools and add an experimental component to it. The experiments are mounted in suitcases which can be borrowed by teachers to perform the experiments in the classroom. Experiments include the hydrogen spectrum, the photo-electric effect, wave-particle duality by means of a double slit experiment with single photons, and a tunneling experiment in which laser light experiences total internal reflection in a prism but some light can tunnel through a wedge of the reflecting surface with a second prism. For the latter two experiments quite a bit of educational engineering was needed to optimize the pedagogy of the experiments and the supporting lesson materials. This was done in collaboration with 5 schools and teachers and 180 students. For our current optimized version retention interviews show that a majority of the students even after 4 and 9 months remember the relevant details and main principles. In the online video presentation, we demonstrate the double slit experiment with single photons and learning results measured 4 months and 9 months after the demonstration. In the break-out group we would like to focus discussion (using online tools) on the role of secondary teachers in UTwente outreach, and on an exchange of ideas about to what extent our methodology for outreach is feasible for other countries and education systems.

3) Nanochemistry: Two modules based on cutting-edge chemistry research were developed. The first module is about early cancer diagnosis, and the second module is about using renewable resources as building blocks for chemicals. These modules were developed by a team of teachers and university researchers and are currently used in chemistry lessons in secondary education. The basis of these learning materials was research that takes place at the Molecular NanoFabrication department at the University of Twente.

In this workshop we will present the design of the module "Early Cancer Diagnosis." Research on the detection of circulating tumor DNA was transformed into learning materials in which students learn about chemical bonding and some cancer chemistry. In the break-out group after the presentation, we moderate a discussion with participants on the possibilities and challenges when designing learning materials based on recent scientific research. Furthermore, we can give the participants a guided tour of our (Dutch language) interactive online lessons on early cancer diagnosis.

After the presentations we will form 3 break-out groups, one for each of the three topics with the questions indicated above for about 15 minutes.

After the break-out sessions we will come together again for 10 minutes and (using online tools) will summarize the strong points and potential weak points of the UTwente outreach approach.

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